

Supplementary tables

Supplementary Table 1. Previously described Insulin-like growth factors 2 (IGF2) transcript variants.

Gene ID	Gene symbol	Transcript	Length (nt)	Protein	Length (aa)	Protein name	Isoform	Transcript name
3841	IGF2	NM_001007139.6	5102	NP_001007140.2	180	insulin-like growth factor II	1 preproprotein	Transcript variant 1
3841	IGF2	NM_001291862.3	4506	NP_001278791.1	180	insulin-like growth factor II	1 preproprotein	Transcript variant 2
3841	IGF2	NM_001127598.3	4671	NP_001121070.1	236	insulin-like growth factor II	2	Transcript variant 3
3841	IGF2	NM_000612.6	5580	NP_000603.1	180	insulin-like growth factor II	1 preproprotein	Transcript variant 4
3841	IGF2	NM_001291861.3	4516	NP_001278790.1	180	insulin-like growth factor II	1 preproprotein	Transcript variant 5

Supplementary Table 2. Melting temperatures (Tms)-based classification.

All samples				GC only				Sp only			
#	Tms	n	%	#	Tms	n	%	#	Tms	n	%
1	89.01	6	6.25%	1	89.01	6	18.75%	1	89.01	0	0.00%
2	88.86	25	26.04%	2	88.86	22	68.75%	2	88.86	3	4.69%
3	88.85	2	2.08%	3	88.85	0	0.00%	3	88.85	2	3.13%
4	88.71	15	15.63%	4	88.71	4	12.50%	4	88.71	11	17.19%
5	88.7	7	7.29%	5	88.7	0	0.00%	5	88.7	7	10.94%
6	88.56	20	20.83%	6	88.56	0	0.00%	6	88.56	20	31.25%
7	88.41	4	4.17%	7	88.41	0	0.00%	7	88.41	4	6.25%
8	88.26	9	9.38%	8	88.26	0	0.00%	8	88.26	9	14.06%
9	88.11	2	2.08%	9	88.11	0	0.00%	9	88.11	2	3.13%
10	78.86	1	1.04%	10	78.86	0	0.00%	10	78.86	1	1.56%
11	78.72	1	1.04%	11	78.72	0	0.00%	11	78.72	1	1.56%
12	72.16	2	2.08%	12	72.16	0	0.00%	12	72.16	2	3.13%
13	71.26	1	1.04%	13	71.26	0	0.00%	13	71.26	1	1.56%
14	71.11	1	1.04%	14	71.11	0	0.00%	14	71.11	1	1.56%
Total		96	100.00%	Total		32	100.00%	Total		64	100.00%

Abbreviations. GC, granulosa cells; Sp, spermatozoa.

Supplementary Table 3. Sequences identified for each colony.

n	Sample	Colony	Sample Name	Tm	Sequence
1	GC	A1	GC_A1	89.01	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
2	GC	B1	GC_B1	88.86	-
3	GC	C1	GC_C1	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
4	GC	D1	GC_D1	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
5	GC	E1	GC_E1	88.86	-
6	GC	F1	GC_F1	88.86	-
7	GC	G1	GC_G1	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
8	GC	H1	GC_H1	89.01	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
9	GC	A2	GC_A2	89.01	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
10	GC	B2	GC_B2	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
11	GC	C2	GC_C2	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
12	GC	D2	GC_D2	88.71	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
13	GC	E2	GC_E2	88.71	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC

					CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
14	GC	F2	GC F2	88.71	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
15	GC	G2	GC G2	88.86	TTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTCCTGCGTG CCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTCGCCCTGAT TGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAAGTGA
16	GC	H2	GC H2	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
17	GC	A3	GC A3	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
18	GC	B3	GC B3	88.86	-
19	GC	C3	GC C3	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
20	GC	D3	GC D3	88.86	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCTGGGGGGGCGCCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGAACGCCTCGAGCTCCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGCCGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTGCGCAGGCGTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAACTT GCCC
21	GC	E3	GC E3	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
22	GC	F3	GC F3	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
23	GC	G3	GC G3	88.71	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCTGGGGGGGCGCCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGAACGCCTCGAGCTCCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGCCGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTTGCAGGCGTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAACTT GCCC
24	GC	H3	GC H3	89.01	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
25	GC	A4	GC A4	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC

					CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
26	GC	B4	GC B4	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
27	GC	C4	GC C4	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
28	GC	D4	GC D4	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
29	GC	E4	GC E4	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
30	GC	F4	GC F4	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
31	GC	G4	GC G4	89.01	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
32	GC	H4	GC H4	89.01	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
33	Sp1	A5	Sp1 A5	88.7	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
34	Sp1	B5	Sp1 B5	88.7	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
35	Sp1	C5	Sp1 C5	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
36	Sp1	D5	Sp1 D5	78.72	-
37	Sp1	E5	Sp1 E5	88.85	-

38	Sp1	F5	Sp1 F5	88.85	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
39	Sp1	G5	Sp1 G5	88.7	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
40	Sp1	H5	Sp1 H5	88.7	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGAACCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGA AGTGA
41	Sp1	A6	Sp1 A6	88.7	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
42	Sp1	B6	Sp1 B6	71.26	-
43	Sp1	C6	Sp1 C6	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
44	Sp1	D6	Sp1 D6	88.56	-
45	Sp1	E6	Sp1 E6	88.7	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGGCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
46	Sp1	F6	Sp1 F6	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
47	Sp1	G6	Sp1 G6	78.86	-
48	Sp1	H6	Sp1 H6	88.7	AGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTCCTGCG TGCCCGCCGGGGTACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTCCTGCG ATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAAGTGA
49	Sp1	A7	Sp1 A7	88.71	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCTGGGGGGGCGCCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGAACGCCTCGAGCTCCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGGCGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTGCGCAGGCGTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAATT GCCC
50	Sp1	B7	Sp1 B7	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
51	Sp1	C7	Sp1 C7	88.56	-
52	Sp1	D7	Sp1 D7	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC

					CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
53	Sp1	E7	Sp1_E7	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
54	Sp1	F7	Sp1_F7	88.71	AGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTCCTGCG TGCCCCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTCCCCTG ATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAAGTGA
55	Sp1	G7	Sp1_G7	88.71	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCYGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
56	Sp1	H7	Sp1_H7	88.86	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
57	Sp1	A8	Sp1_A8	88.86	-
58	Sp1	B8	Sp1_B8	72.16	-
59	Sp1	C8	Sp1_C8	88.41	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCTGGGGGGGCGCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGAACGCCTTGAGTCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGCGGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTGCGCAGGCGCTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAACTT GCCC
60	Sp1	D8	Sp1_D8	88.56	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCTGGGGGGGCGCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGAACGCCTCGAGTCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGCGGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTGCGCAGGCGCTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAACTT GCCC
61	Sp1	E8	Sp1_E8	88.41	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCTGGGGGGGCGCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGAACGCCTCGAGTCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGACGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTGCGCAGGCGCTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAACTT GCCC
62	Sp1	F8	Sp1_F8	88.71	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCTGGGGGGGCGCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGAACGCCTCGAGTCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGCGGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTGCGCAGGCGCTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAACTT GCCC
63	Sp1	G8	Sp1_G8	71.11	-
64	Sp1	H8	Sp1_H8	88.71	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCTGGGGGGGCGCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGAACGCCTCGAGTCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGCGGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTGCGCAGGCGCTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAACTT GCCC
65	Sp2	A9	Sp2_A9	88.71	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA

66	Sp2	B9	Sp2 B9	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
67	Sp2	C9	Sp2 C9	88.56	-
68	Sp2	D9	Sp2 D9	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
69	Sp2	E9	Sp2 E9	88.56	-
70	Sp2	F9	Sp2 F9	88.71	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
71	Sp2	G9	Sp2 G9	88.86	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCTGGGGGGGCGCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGGACGCCTCGAGCTCCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGGCGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTGCGCAGGCGCTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAAGT GCCC
72	Sp2	H9	Sp2 H9	72.16	-
73	Sp2	A10	Sp2 A10	88.71	-
74	Sp2	B10	Sp2 B10	88.56	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCTGGGGGGGCGCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGAACGCCTCGAGCTCCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGGCGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTGCGCAGGCGCTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAAGT GCCC
75	Sp2	C10	Sp2 C10	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
76	Sp2	D10	Sp2 D10	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
77	Sp2	E10	Sp2 E10	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
78	Sp2	F10	Sp2 F10	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
79	Sp2	G10	Sp2 G10	88.71	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA

80	Sp2	H10	Sp2 H10	88.71	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
81	Sp2	A11	Sp2 A11	88.26	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
82	Sp2	B11	Sp2 B11	88.26	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
83	Sp2	C11	Sp2 C11	88.11	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
84	Sp2	D11	Sp2 D11	88.26	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
85	Sp2	E11	Sp2 E11	88.71	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGGGATGGCCAGCAATCGGA AGTGA
86	Sp2	F11	Sp2 F11	88.26	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
87	Sp2	G11	Sp2 G11	88.41	-
88	Sp2	H11	Sp2 H11	88.56	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
89	Sp2	A12	Sp2 A12	88.26	AGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTCCTGCG TGCCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC ATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAAGTGA
90	Sp2	B12	Sp2 B12	88.11	-
91	Sp2	C12	Sp2 C12	88.26	TCACTTCCGATTGCTGGCCATCTCCGGGGGGCGCCCCGTGGGCGGGGTCTTGGGTGGGTAGAGCAATC AGGGGACGGTGACGTTTGGCCTCCCTGAACGCCTCGAGCTCCTTGGCGAGCACGTGACCCCGCGGGCAC GCAGGAGGGCAGGCAGGCCCTGCGCAGGCGTGGGTGGACTGCTTCCAGGTGTCATATTGGAAGAAGTT GCC
92	Sp2	D12	Sp2 D12	88.26	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTACCCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA

93	Sp2	E12	Sp2 E12	88.26	GGGCAAGTTCTTCCAATATGACACCTGGAAGCAGTCCACCCAGCGCCTGCGCAGGGGCCTGCCTGCCCTC CTGCGTGCCCGCCGGGGTCACGTGCTCGCCAAGGAGCTCGAGGCGTTCAGGGAGGCCAAACGTCACCGTC CCCTGATTGCTCTACCCACCCAAGACCCCGCCACGGGGGCGCCCCCAGAGATGGCCAGCAATCGGAA GTGA
94	Sp2	F12	Sp2 F12	88.26	-
95	Sp2	G12	Sp2 G12	88.41	-
96	Sp2	H12	Sp2 H12	88.56	-

Abbreviations. GC, granulosa cells; Sp1, spermatozoa from donor 1; Sp2, spermatozoa from donor 2.

Supplementary Table 4. Results of sequence alignment analysis.

Sequence	Nucleotides number	Changes	Amino acid number	Changes in the amino acid sequence (vs. Seq #1)
Seq#1	214	-	71	-
Seq#2	215	del (1-3); C→T (4); A→C (5); G→C (7); T→C (11); T→G (12); C→A (13); C→T (14); A→T (15); A→G (16); T→C (17); A→T (18); T→G (19); A→C (21); C→T (24); G→C (27); G→T (28); A→G (29); A→G (30); C→G (32); A→G (33); T→G (35); C→G (37); A→C (38); del (42-45); C→G (47); C→G (50); A→G (53); G→T (57); C→T (59); G→C (62); C→G (63); C→G (66); del (68); C→A (70); C→G (71); T→A (72); G→A (75); T→A (76); G→T (77); C→A (79); C→G (80); C→G (82); C→G (83); G→A (84); G→C (85); C→G (89); G→T (94); ins(95-98); G→C (102); C→T (104); A→G (105); G→A (107); G→C (108); A→G (109); G→C (110); G→C (117); C→T (118); G→C (119); T→C (120); C→T (122); A→G (123); G→C (125); G→C (129); del (130-133); C→G (138); G→C (142); T→C (143); C→G (144); C→G (145); C→G (146); C→G (147); T→G (148); A→C (150); A→C (150); T→A (151); T→C (152); T→A (155); C→G (156); T→G (157); C→G (159); C→G (160); ins(161); C→G (164); C→G (165); A→G (168); A→C (170); C→T (174); C→G (177); C→G (180); C→G (182); ins(184-186); C→T (189); C→G (191); C→A (192); C→T (194); C→G (195); C→T (197); ins(198); A→C (199); G→C (200); A→G (203); G→T (206); C→A (208); A→T (209); G→A (210); C→T (211); A→T (212); A→G (213); T→G (214); C→A (215); G→A (216); G→C (220); G→T (222); A→G (223); ins(224-226) vs. Seq#1	71	Yes vs. Seq#1
Seq#3	209	del (1-5) vs. Seq#1	71	Yes vs. Seq#1
Seq#4	207	del (1-7) vs. Seq#1	69	Yes vs. Seq#1
Seq#5	214	C→T (173) vs. Seq#2	71	Yes vs. Seq#2
Seq#6	215	A→G (90) vs. Seq#1	71	No vs. Seq#1
Seq#7	214	C→A (171); ins(198) vs. Seq#1	71	Yes vs. Seq#1
Seq#8	214	A→G (170) vs. Seq#1	71	Yes vs. Seq#1
Seq#9	214	Y(26) vs. Seq#1	71	Yes vs. Seq#1
Seq#10	214	C→T (113) vs. Seq#2	71	Yes vs. Seq#2
Seq#11	214	G→A (145) vs. Seq#2	71	Yes vs. Seq#2
Seq#12	214	A→G (106) vs. Seq#2	71	Yes vs. Seq#2
Seq#13	215	Ins(198); A→G (201) vs. Seq#1	71	Yes vs. Seq#1
Seq#14	214	T→C (28) vs. Seq#2	71	Yes vs. Seq#2

The numbers in brackets refer to the nucleotide site.

Legend to Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Sequence analysis. *Panel A.* A total of 14 unique sequences were identified. Seq #1 and Seq #2 were the most frequent and were shared by both sperm- and GC-derived colonies. Seq #4 and Seq #5 were exclusively identified in GC-derived colonies, while the remaining sequences were specific to sperm-derived colonies. ***Panel B.*** The chart displays the sample in which each sequence was identified, along with the corresponding melting temperatures (Tms). Tms were not specific to individual sequences, and many overlapped across the different sequences. Abbreviations. GC, granulosa cell; Sp1, spermatozoa from patient 1; Sp2, spermatozoa from patient 2.